

Effect of Geometric Asymmetry on Thermal Performance in Non-Coaxial L-shape Oscillating Heat Pipe

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Abstract

The paper investigates the performance of a novel oscillating heat pipe with a unique L-shaped geometry, where the evaporator is oriented at a 90° angle to the condenser. The experiment explores the influence of gravitational acceleration by adjusting the system's inclination angle across a full range from 0° to 180°, using acetone as the working fluid. The capillary tube has an inner diameter of 1.5 mm, enabling the formation of liquid plugs and vapor bubbles. Three filling ratios were evaluated: 50%, 70%, and 80%, with a maximum applied heat flux of 43 kW m⁻². Under optimal conditions, the thermal resistance was found to be 0.48 K W⁻¹. The findings indicate that the geometric design and orientation relative to Earth's gravitational field have a significant impact on the oscillating heat pipe's thermal performance. Despite having relatively few bends, the device achieved efficient horizontal heat transfer under certain conditions. Notably, these results, particularly for high filling ratios, have not been reported in previous studies. Additionally, the research enhances the analysis of oscillating heat pipes, with the thermal resistance trends providing valuable insights into start-up behavior, overheating risk, and distinct operating modes.

Keywords: Oscillating heat pipe, Pulsating heat pipe, Multiphase, Effective

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thermal conductivity

Nomenclature

Symbols

A	area (m^2)
c_p	specific heat ($J/(kgK)$)
g	gravitational acceleration (m/s^2)
h_{vap}	latent heat of vaporization (J/kg)
J	volumetric mass flux ($kg/(m^3 s)$)
k	thermal conductivity ($W/(m K)$)
L	length (m)
p	pressure (Pa)
q	heat flux (W/m^2)
R	gas constant ($J/(kgK)$)
T	temperature (K)
t	time (s)
U	velocity vector (m/s)
Z	compressibility factor (-)
Bo	Bond number ()
Me_{CHP}	Merit number for conventional heat pipe (kg/s^3)
Me_{PHP}	Merit number for pulsating heat pipe ($Pa/(sK^2)$)

Greek symbols

α	volume fraction
β	relaxation factor (1/s)
κ	curvature proximity (1/m)
μ	dynamic viscosity ($Pa \cdot s$)
ν	kinematic viscosity (m^2/s)
ϕ	scalar value at interface
ρ	density (kg/m^3)

σ surface tension coefficient (N/m)

Subscripts

ad	adiabatic section
cr	cross-sectional
eff	effective
in	internal
l	liquid phase
lv	from liquid phase to vapor phase
sat	parameter in saturation state
v	vapor phase
vl	from vapor phase to liquid phase

Abbreviations

AI	artificial intelligence
DC	direct current
DOE	design of experiment
ECHA	european chemicals agency
EPA	environmental protection agency
FR	filling ratio
GASP	general anti-particle spectrometer
GPIB	general-purpose interface bus
MAD	mean absolute deviation
NMD	normalized mean derivative
OHP	oscillating heat pipe
PETG	polyethylene terephthalate glycol
PFAS	perFluoroAlkyl substances
PHP	pulsating heat pipe
WF	working fluid

1. Introduction

Today's rapid development of technology presents both challenges and opportunities for the scientific community. Each field strives to adapt to these changes and thus meet the growing demand for knowledge and skills. Regarding environmental protection, low-energy power consumption systems and passive devices that provide high thermal performance are particularly valuable [1]. An example of this is the oscillating heat pipe (OHP), which meets the requirements for efficient functionality. OHP's have an effective thermal conductivity that can be 800 times greater than that of pure copper [2] without the need for an additional external energy supply. This solution presents a notable advantage in its simplicity, characterized by the sole utilization of a meandering bent capillary in its basic design. OHP potential extends beyond geometric features, including promising aspects such as the feasibility of miniaturization, shape modifications, and seamless integration with the working fluid (WF). In particular, the variable in the system is not only the type of WF and its thermo-physical properties, but also other features such as the filling ratio (FR) [3, 4], inclination angle [5, 6], channel dimensions [7, 8], and power density [9, 10]. By adjusting the operating parameters to the specified boundary conditions, these variables are selected so that the heat transfer process can be carried out in the most efficient manner possible. Consequently, scientific research can yield a diverse array of conclusions.

When selecting a working fluid, the use of acetone in OHP has yielded promising results in several studies. Bhagat et al. [11] determined that a filling ratio of 60% is optimal for enhancing the thermal performance of a closed-loop oscillating heat pipe, using acetone as the WF. This conclusion is also supported by Samadi et al. [12], who compared the use of water, acetone, methanol, and ethanol as WFs and also found the filling ratio 60% as the optimal value. Zhu et al. [13] added to these findings by demonstrating that incorporating water into acetone can improve start-up performance and prevent dry-out. Rahman et al. [14] expanded on this by observing that, in an open loop OHP, acetone

outperformed distilled water, especially at a 70 % filling ratio at a relatively low power input. These studies collectively demonstrate the potential of acetone as a working fluid in oscillating heat pipes, particularly at a 60 % to 70 % of FR.

Wang et al. [15] explored the thermal resistance of acetone-water mixtures compared to pure fluids. They found that at high power loads the thermal resistance of the acetone-water mixture was between that of pure compounds. However, when acetone was mixed with ethanol or methanol in ratios of 2 : 1 and 4 : 1, the thermal resistance was lower than that of pure fluids, but only in a medium filling ratio of 55 %. At higher FRs of 62 % and 70 %, the thermal resistance of the mixture was higher than that of the pure fluids. In summary, it is important to note that the efficiency of OHPs depends on the properties of the working fluid or material [16], and the presented studies were carried out using a flow channel shape similar to the flat-plate OHP configuration, wherein all sections were linearly arranged with an axial alignment.

In the context of geometry, the OHP heat transfer performance in an OHP significantly depends not only on internal diameter [17], heating and cooling areas or length [18], but also on the shape and geometrical configuration of the OHPs themselves. The primary distinction lies in technology, which can be classified into flat plate OHPs, tubular OHPs, and 3D OHPs [9, 10]. According to Takawale et al. [19], these designs exhibit different oscillation amplitudes, leading to varying thermal performances. Flat plate OHPs offer limited geometric variations because the grooves must be machined into the plate. However, they are preferable for integration into the system when compared to tubular OHPs [20]. Extensive research has been conducted on flat plate OHPs [21]. For example, Chen et al. [22] proposed a novel solution that combined two systems into a single flat-plate OHP with tandem dual channels. They reported achieving approximately 6.5 times lower thermal resistance compared to pure aluminum 6063. Ibrahim et al. [23] presented a solution for a printed PHP, which may be considered as a multi-layered flat-plate. The investigation was evaluated in terms of orientation and working fluid. Their examination concluded that thermal performance exhibited a high degree of independence from

operating orientation and that the application of acetone as the WF resulted in reduced start-up power and enhanced more effective operation in various orientations. Often, the focus of research is on the geometric variations of the evaporator and condenser, such as that found in an OHP multilayer system [24]. Han et al. [25] proposed a 3D-printed polymer-based flexible oscillating heat pipe (FOHP) for thermal management with the conception of a setup similar to the experiment presented in this work. Ethanol was used as the working fluid and a fill ratio of 40% provided optimal performance with the lowest thermal resistance. The FOHP, bendable up to 90° , effectively managed heat in flexible printed circuit. Qu et al. [26] experimentally investigated the thermal performance of a multilayer, three-dimensional OHP. This study examined three variables: the number of layers (ranging from 2 to 5), orientation (vertical and horizontal) and filling ratio (30%, 50% and 70%). Furthermore, the authors of this study tested both 2D (planar) and 3D (spatially modified) configurations. In the 3D configuration, four layers were determined to be optimal in terms of start-up temperature and thermal resistance. This research also verified that as the number of layers increased, both the temperature difference and the thermal resistance decreased. The authors concluded that with low heat flux, the 3D configuration did not perform as well as the 2D configuration, which had a higher temperature and greater thermal resistance. However, when operating at a higher heat flux, the situation reversed and the 2D configuration was less effective. Layers can also exist separately as independent closed-loop OHPs (CLOHPs), as demonstrated by Wei et al. [27].

A notable proposal by Okazaki et al. [28] focuses on the OHP shape. The authors investigated two geometric configurations: an "O" shape and a "U" shape, for application in general anti-particle spectrometer. Their experimental studies showed that the O-shaped OHP operates effectively in both room and low temperature ranges, meeting design requirements. It also requires a lower minimum starting-up heat load and reaches steady state more quickly at low temperatures compared to the U-shaped OHP. Fuke et al. [29] proposed a similar design, where one leg of the "U" shape was inclined. This configuration

was tested during a balloon flight, marking the first successful demonstration of an OHP in the sky. The authors reported a thermal conductance of 5 W K^{-1} for the tested OHP. Another geometric solution is presented by He et al. [30], who examined a three-dimensional OHP with tandem trapped nozzles as an asymmetrical option and compared them to a typical OHP with a uniform internal diameter. The thermal resistance of the asymmetrical close-loop OHP decreased by 29.5%, indicating that the tandem tapered nozzles significantly improve heat transfer performance.

In addition to shape, the number of turns is also crucial. Deng et al. [31] introduced an OHP under an antigravity operation, suggesting that the critical number of turns, which makes pulsating heat pipe independent of the gravitational field, varies according to parameters such as inner diameter, heat flux, and physical properties of WF. Their experiments showed that this critical number is equal to 15 turns. In studying OHP systems using acetone as the working fluid, researchers have focused on how orientation affects performance in both tubular and flat-plate designs. Halimi et al. [32] investigated the impact of gravity on the thermal performance of the tubular system. Their investigation revealed that increasing the number of turns in an OHP enhances the thermal performance while simultaneously mitigating the influence of working fluid.

A novel flower-shaped design similar to the L-shaped was first proposed in a rotating setup by Czajkowski et al. [33] and was further investigated in a stationary setup by Chen et al. [34], who explored an asymmetric design with turns only in the evaporator section. Meanwhile, Czajkowski et al. [33] designed an OHP that mirrored the evaporator and condenser sections. Using acetone as the working fluid with a filling ratio of 50%, Chen's team [34] achieved the best performance, with a thermal resistance of 0.14 K W^{-1} . This stationary flower shape setup ($\omega = 0 \text{ RPM}$), used deionized water as working fluid with a filling ratio of 50%, the thermal resistance was even lower (i.e., equal to 0.017 K W^{-1}). Kammuang-Lue et al. [35] and On-ai et al. [36] also explored specific shapes for rotating OHPs by examining the effects of varying diameters, working fluids, and temperatures under the influence of external forces. They

[35, 36] concluded that a higher latent heat leads to a lower pressure difference between the evaporator and the condenser, increasing the thermal resistance of the system. External forces were found to increase the flow, leading to higher frequency variations in temperature. However, these studies did not compare the impact of changing the tube geometry from a standard meander to a cross-like shape. Many experimental works have focused on the directional effect of the acceleration vector in the Earth's gravitational field, such as the tilt angle [37] or top-mode heating [38]. However, it should be noted that a wide range of research focuses on the uniform shape of the oscillating heat pipe, where external forces act equally on each of the three sections of the device, perpendicular to the axis of the flow channel. The proposed solution of bending the evaporation section into an L-shaped form has not been prominently discussed in the current literature review.

This study investigates the impact of geometric asymmetry on the thermal performance of a oscillating heat pipe. The research focuses on the full range of tilt angles, from horizontal to vertical and back, as well as high filling ratio. These factors, combined with the unique geometric shape, have not been proposed or studied together before. In addition, thermal analysis involves testing the device at different power levels to fully assess its heat transfer performance. This study expands on our previously prepared experimental test stand used in the publication of preliminary results [39], which focused on the influence of centrifugal acceleration on thermal performance. The experimental setup has been modified to explore combined impact under stationary conditions for different diameter and working fluid. Unlike the prior work, which analyzed dynamic forces, the present research investigates the effect of inclination angle on thermal and flow characteristics, offering new insights into the system's behavior in steady-state condition.

2. Experimental set-up

In this study, an OHP test stand with a horizontally bent evaporation section was employed. While a similar setup was previously utilized by Czajkowski et al. [39] and Opalski et al. [40], the test stand was adapted and modified to meet the specific requirements of the present research. The following subsections contain a detailed description of the system components, as shown in Figure 1, as well as a description of the data acquisition and processing procedures.

Figure 1: Experimental setup: a) OHP, b) Exp. test stand., c) Inclination of configuration.

2.1. Oscillating heat pipe

During the experimental phase, a copper capillary pipe (with an internal diameter of 1.5 mm and a wall thickness of 1 mm) was utilized along with borosilicate glass (4 pieces with a wall thickness of 2.5 mm). To satisfy optimal operational conditions for substances with lower surface tensions than water, the

selection of the internal diameter was based on the dimensionless Bond number (Bo) expressed as described in Equation (1).

$$Bo = \frac{(\rho_l - \rho_v) \cdot g \cdot d_{in}^2}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

Acetone was selected as the working fluid based on the relatively high value of the Merit number for conventional heat pipe (Me_{CHP}) together with Merit number for pulsating heat pipe (Me_{PHP}) [41] defined by Equation (2) and Equation (3), respectively.

$$Me_{CHP} = \frac{\sigma \rho_l h_{fg}}{\mu_l} \quad (2)$$

$$Me_{PHP} = \frac{\rho_l c_{pl} (dP/dT)_{sat} Z R T_{sat}}{\mu_l h_{fg}} \quad (3)$$

The choice of this working fluid was also due to the restrictions currently considered by the european chemicals agency (ECHA) and environmental protection agency (EPA) regarding perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). The study investigates the effect of the filling ratio of 50 % [15, 14], 70 % [42], and 80 % [43].

2.2. Experimental test stand

The condensation section was equipped with a thermal bath using the Bolid *B300B/5.5/H-C* device, paired with two Saber *NGR-23* pumps to maintain a constant volumetric flow rate of the medium at a temperature of $T = 288\text{ K}$ (water, $\dot{V} = 10\text{ l/min}$). Temperature measurements were obtained using T-type thermocouples with a diameter of 0.1 mm, while the coolant flow was monitored using an ultrasonic flowmeter flowmax[®] 44i.

The heating section used a jacketed resistance wire (Inconel 600, 0.89 mm in diameter) connected in series. The thermal insulation was comprised of a double layer of polycrystalline wool with mullite and corundum (ALSIFLEX[®]) where $k = 0.08\text{ W/mK}$ for 400°C with one 10 mm thick layer for the evaporation section, low thermal conductivity glass ($\lambda = 1.12\text{ W/mK}$) for the quasi-adiabatic

Table 1: Thermodynamic properties of acetone at 20 °C.

Name of parameter	Value	Unit
Boiling point at atmospheric pressure	329	<i>K</i>
Saturation pressure	30.390	<i>kPa</i>
Pressure drop	1.110	<i>kPa/K</i>
Latent heat of vaporization	558.866	<i>kJ/kg</i>
Liquid density	790	<i>kg/m³</i>
Vapor density	0.6	<i>kg/m³</i>
Dynamic viscosity	$7.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	<i>mPa · s</i>
Surface tension	23	<i>mN/m</i>
Liquid specific heat	2.140	<i>kJ/kg · K</i>
Thermal conductivity	0.18	<i>W/m · K</i>
Critical tube diameter ¹	3.46	<i>mm</i>

¹ Critical tube diameter is calculated by $d_{crit} = 2\sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{g(\rho_l - \rho_v)}}$, with *CoolProp* [44]

section, and polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) material with a 15 mm thickness for the condensation section. This configuration ensured negligible thermal losses. The evaporation section was connected to a direct current (DC) power supply through a general-purpose interface bus (GPIB) port (Agilent Technologies, USA) to allow simultaneous measurements of voltage and current at the heater junction.

The tilt adjustments were controlled using an inertial motion sensor (STMicroelectronics *LSM6DSO*). The experimental setup as shown in Fig. 1 was modified to allow adjustments in the tilt angle, facilitating experiments at seven orientations from horizontal forward to backward positions. This was done to assess the impact of bending on thermal performance. A vacuum seal was maintained with EPDM O-rings and specialized high vacuum components (Idex[®] Corporation). The pressure measurements used a pressure transducer (Wika, *S – 20*), and a *CompactDAQ – 9178* data acquisition (National Instruments) for the pressure and temperature measurements.

2.3. Measurement procedure

The measurement procedure consists simultaneous acquisition of temperature, pressure, volumetric flow rate, voltage, and current data. Thermal processes were controlled using LabView software (v.2022Q3) to ensure safety against overheating or excessive pressure build-up. Non-condensable gas removal was conducted using a scroll pump (nXDS10i, EDWARDS LC, UK) and a helium detector (Pfeiffer[®] VACUUM ASM 340). To evaluate the impact of evaporator bending, three different working fluid filling ratios was used which required unit drying and leakage testing. Each time oscillating heat pipe was tested under vacuum condition. Changes in pressure reading inside oscillating heat pipe indicated a potential leakage. Once the integrity of the system was confirmed safe, working fluid was introduced using sealed piston vessels with capacities of 5 ml (for 50 % and 70 % filling ratio) and 10 ml (for 80 % filling ratio), following OHP vacuuming, fluid degassing, and its injection. The next series of measurements started when the saturation pressure of the working fluid was achieved after two heating cycles under the maximum thermal load. The data recording started at a mean temperature of 23 °C in the evaporation section to minimize the influence of the operational condition. Each measurement series involved intervals of changes in the heater power level, as detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: The values of the heat load provided during the experiment.

Time interval <i>s</i>	Heat Input <i>W</i>	Heat flux <i>kW/m²</i>	Abbrev.\Round <i>-kW/m²</i>
0 – 1800.0	6.97	2.64	<i>Q₁ \ 3</i>
1800.8 – 2400.0	14.14	5.36	<i>Q₂ \ 5</i>
2400.8 – 3000.0	28.31	10.73	<i>Q₃ \ 11</i>
3000.8 – 3600.0	42.45	16.09	<i>Q₄ \ 16</i>
3600.8 – 4200.0	56.64	21.46	<i>Q₅ \ 21</i>
4200.8 – 4800.0	84.98	32.18	<i>Q₆ \ 32</i>
4800.8 – 5400.0	113.25	42.88	<i>Q₇ \ 43</i>

2.4. Data reduction and uncertainty

The temperature of each section is calculated by the arithmetic mean according Equation (4).

$$\bar{T}_{e,c}^1 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N T_i \quad (4)$$

The frequency of recording measurement data was equal to 1.25 Hz. During injection of working fluid, instruments with a resolution of 0.1 ml and 0.2 ml was used. The volumetric error for filling ratios was as follows: 50 % ($\pm 3.1\%$), 70 % ($\pm 2.2\%$) and 80 % ($\pm 3.85\%$). The complete characterization of the additional measurement apparatus is provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Characterisation of measured parameters.

Parameter	Accuracy	Standard uncer.	Abbrev.
Voltage	$\pm 0.04\%+120$ mV	0.088 V	uU
Current	$\pm 0.1\%+12$ mA	0.008 A	uI
Temperature	± 0.5 °C	0.3 °C	uT
Pressure	± 1000 Pa	577 Pa	uP
Length	± 0.01 mm	0.006 mm	uL
Volum. flow	± 0.31 /min	0.21/min	$u\dot{V}$
Tilt angle	± 1 °	0.6°	$u\theta$

The measurement values for temperature and pressure were determined with expanded uncertainties, including terms for the measurement accuracy of the NI modules (9212TB = 0.36 °C, 9201 = 0.25 %), resulting in uncertainties of ± 0.7 °C for temperature and ± 1155 Pa for pressure. The uncertainties in the derived quantities were determined following the methodology outlined by Kline and McClintock [45]. The propagation of error resulting from uncertainty in measured physical quantities in thermal resistance calculation is detailed in Equation (5).

¹Where e represents N=6 and c represents value of 7

$$\delta R = \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial \Delta T} \cdot \delta(\Delta T)\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial Q} \cdot \delta Q\right)^2} \quad (5)$$

Table 4 lists the calculated results for the propagation of uncertainty under the final assumption of a critical coefficient $k = 2$ for a confidence level of 95%.

Table 4: Propagation of uncertainty.

Parameter	Formula	Expanded uncer.	Abbrev.
Temp. diff.	$\Delta T = \bar{T}_e - \bar{T}_c$	$\pm 2.1^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta(\Delta T)$
Heat transfer	$\dot{Q} = U \cdot I$	$\pm 1.21 \text{ W}$	$\Delta\dot{Q}$
Thermal res.	$R = \Delta T/Q$	$\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C/W}$	ΔR
Heat flux	$\dot{q} = \dot{Q}/A$	$\pm 0.98 \text{ kW/m}^2$	$\Delta\dot{q}$

Each set of measurements is compared to the others, necessitating the determination of average values for thermal process parameters at specific time intervals. Changes in power levels over time are evaluated based on the last measurements within each power range. The key metrics to evaluate the heat transfer performance of an OHP include thermal resistance, as shown in Table 4, and effective thermal conductivity, as defined by Equation (6).

$$k_{eff} = \frac{Q}{\bar{T}_e - \bar{T}_c} \cdot \frac{L_{ad}}{A_{crin}} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) describes the thermal efficiency of the system under specific operating conditions. For a comprehensive understanding, it is useful to analyze the signals obtained, which focus on detecting:

- Process stability: determination whether transient or steady-state conditions were achieved.
- Overheating phenomenon: checking whether the start-up condition was met during the first two steps of power input variation.
- Flow mode: identifying the operating mode between oscillating (unstable in terms of temperature amplitude) and directional (achieving a circulating flow).

This approach is a novel method in the field of OHPs. Therefore, a detailed description of the analysis conducted is provided. The derivative of the thermal resistance was first calculated, as presented in Equation (7),

$$R'(t) \approx \frac{\delta R}{\delta t} \approx \frac{R(t + \Delta t) - R(t)}{\Delta t} \quad (7)$$

and obtain an average derivative of the thermal resistance based on Equation (8).

$$\overline{R'(t)} \approx \frac{\sum_{i=a}^b R'(t_i)}{n} \quad (8)$$

The normalized mean derivative (NMD) can be found by Equation (9),

$$NMD = \frac{\overline{R'(t)}}{R'_{max}} \quad (9)$$

and the mean absolute deviation (MAD) can be expressed by Equation (10).

$$MAD = \frac{\sum_{i=a}^b |R'(t_i) - \overline{R'(t)}|}{n} \quad (10)$$

In the final step, the derivative differences can be determined as presented in Equation (11),

$$\Delta R'(t)_{[a,b]} \approx \Delta \left(\frac{\delta R}{\delta t} \right) \approx R'(t_{i+1}) - R'(t_i) \quad (11)$$

where $a = b - 3000$ for $Q = Q_1$ or $a = b - 1000$ for $Q > Q_1$ and b is maximal value of time in each interval.

Linear regression was performed using LinearModelFit to analyze the trends of derivative value trends. This approach allows for the fitting of a linear model to the data, enabling an examination of the slope of the fitted line to define whether its directional component is positive (indicative of a rising trend), zero (indicating a flat trend) or negative (suggesting a declining trend). Thus, it can be determined whether transient ($s > 0$) or steady-state ($s \leq 0$) conditions were achieved.

Figure 2 describes a mean and difference calculation for derivatives of thermal resistance for tested results at a filling ratio of 70% and a inclination angle

of 120° . The results shown in Figure 2 can be used to assess the operating mode to determine whether the flow character inside the OHP is pulsating or unidirectional, also known as the circulating flow. The calculations outline the methodology to assess operating conditions essential for comprehending the nature of the thermal-flow process and determining its stability and characteristics.

Figure 2: Example of a mean and differences calculations for derivative of thermal resistance in case of 70 % at 120° : *Data*₁-pulsating flow, *Data*_{2,3}-unidirectional flow.

3. Results and discussion

The measurement campaign included tests aimed at evaluating repeatability and examining the impact of various factors inherent to the thermal process, such as filling ratio, inclination angle, and power supply value. The schedule describing these tests is detailed in Table 5. The first set experiment was labeled "Test No.1", while repetitions were represented by the group of results for "Test No.2". The acceptance marks indicate a successfully conducted study, while the cross marks refer to studies that were not performed due to a clear tendency to process deterioration. Cells were grouped into sets according to the value of the FR (notations in the row from the top) and their corresponding tilt angle (notations in the row from the bottom).

Table 5: Values of the filling ratio and inclination angles provided during the experiment

Filling Ratio																	
50%						70%						80%					
Test No. 1																	
✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Test No. 2																	
✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
0	30	60	90	120	150	180	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	0	30	60	90
Angle																	

3.1. Assessment of repeatability: a two-measurement analysis

In the primary experimental phase, repeatability tests were performed. Figure 3 illustrates tests in which OHP operating conditions were repeated in the vertical position. Consistent trends were found throughout the experiment, particularly in the medium power supply range. However, variations in operating conditions were observed at different stages in all three cases.

In instances of lower filling ratios, instability was observed within the higher range of power supply values, particularly with respect to Q_3 . In contrast, in scenarios characterized by higher filling ratio, instability manifested solely at the initial power level, Q_1 , with subsequent steps demonstrating relatively consistent behavior under both experimental conditions. The middle filling ratio exhibited the greatest discrepancy in the results of the vertical position tests, both for the low and high power values. Those results revealed a significant difference in thermal resistance. It should be noted that in the middle power range, that is, from Q_2 to Q_4 , the convergence of the results is satisfactory.

Taking into account the variable values of the thermal resistance obtained under consistent operating conditions, an analysis of the deviation between the results of the mean thermal resistance was carried out. It is difficult to investigate intermediate states while simultaneously determining local instabilities. Therefore, in this paper, the focus is on the deepest possible steady states, thus at the final time zone of each heating stage (as mentioned in Subsection 2.4).

(a) Lower filling ratio.

(b) Medium filling ratio.

(c) Higher filling ratio.

Figure 3: Repeatability tests at various filling ratios in a vertical position (Red lines: Test no.1 and Green Lines: Test no.2 - repeated test).

The results are shown in Table 6. The mean of the observed minimum and maximum deviations were equal to 6.1% and 35.9%, respectively. Values exceeding the mean max are marked with a pink background. Based on the findings presented, the results show repeatability. However, the test stand demonstrates local instabilities, which can possibly be attributed to the specific geometry of the OHP evaporation section.

Table 6: Convergence analysis compares results for Test No.1 and Test No.2 serving as a deviation between experiments. - values over mean value.

		Filling Ratio																	
		50%			70%			80%											
		Min. deviation, %																	
	2.2	15.7	17.1	0.0	1.7	2.3	7.7	3.2	1.5	20.7	1	0.8	18	6.8	2.3	2.4	2.1	5.3	
		Max. deviation, %																	
	2.2	37.9	89.4	17.9	1.7	47.9	13.8	56.2	22	63.5	1	0.8	37.5	88	26.3	62.8	61.3	15.5	
Angle		0	30	60	90	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	0	30	60	90	120	150	180

3.2. Thermal resistance measurements under variable conditions

Figure 4 displays thermal resistance profiles, revealing a clear start-up presence for inclinations ranging between 30° and 90°. However, the remaining three studies indicate that the system was overheating, requiring the discontinuation of further tests. System overheating conditions were observed for Q_2 on slopes of 0°, 120° and 150°, for Q_4 at 30° and 60°, and for Q_5 at 90°. The vertical position exhibited the highest stability during the first heating stage, while instabilities were noted as early as the third heating stage for the two preceding inclinations. Throughout the measurement range, including operating time, low thermal resistance, and stability, the vertical position yielded the best parameters, while efficient oscillating heat pipe operation conditions were not reached in the horizontal position.

Figure 5 includes a comprehensive test matrix. This was carried out because

Figure 4: Effects of power input and titled angle on the thermal resistance at a FR=50 %

the alteration of the angle does not exhibit a clear trend toward the deterioration of the thermal parameters. In this scenario, the extreme inclination values (0° and 180°) indicated the most challenging operating conditions. Complete start-up was achieved only within the range of $< 30^\circ$ and $150^\circ >$. Once again, circumstances similar to the previous scenario appear and the vertical position shows the most favorable operating parameters up to the third heating stage. Efficient oscillating heat pipe operation conditions were not achieved in the horizontal position.

Figure 5: Effects of power input and titled angle on the thermal resistance at a FR=70 %.

The maximum value of thermal resistance characterizing the absence of the

start-up phenomenon exceeded 8 K W^{-1} , while the lowest value, $R = 0.48 \text{ K W}^{-1}$, was obtained for the vertical position and the third heating stage. The tilt backward or forward was by 30° , compared to the vertical position, which similarly exhibited relatively low thermal resistance and steady-state process conditions. However, it should be noted that under optimal conditions (Q_3), the thermal resistance value, R , increased by approximately 40% for tilting forward and by approximately 60% for tilting backward.

Figure 6: Effects of power input and titled angle on the thermal resistance at a FR=80%.

Significant differences in the performance characteristics of the OHP were obtained for the high filling ratio, as presented in Figure 6. The lack of start-up conditions can only be observed for position 0° . This time, when tilted forward by 30° , from a vertical position, the entire measurement range was clear and proved to be the best case. It should be noted that the OHP operated even in horizontal position (moving forward). Most of the tests were interrupted by automatic protection against excessive pressure (excluding the 0° and 30° cases). The results in the horizontal position for a forward tilt demonstrate that it is crucial to ensure wetting of the evaporator surface (appropriate FR) and the direction of the evaporator bend (aligned with the vector direction of acceleration in the gravitational field of Earth).

Once again, as in previous instances, the maximum thermal resistance value that indicates the absence of the start-up phenomenon exceeded 8 K W^{-1} . This

Figure 7: Normalized mean for derivative of thermal resistance in the case of FR=70%.

time, the lowest value of $R = 0.78, \text{K W}^{-1}$ was achieved for a forward tilt of 120° during the third heating stage. The vertical position and a further forward tilt by an additional 30° exhibited similarly relatively low thermal resistance values and steady-state process conditions. However, it should be noted that under optimal conditions (Q_3), the thermal resistance value, R , increased by approximately 15% for the vertical position and by approximately 20% for the tilt equal to 150° .

3.3. Operating characteristics analysis

As described in Subsection 2.4 the start-up condition and the overheating phenomenon could be calculated according to Eqs. (9) and (10). It is evident that system overheating can be identified by values that exceed the average threshold, typically around 0.36, Figure 7. However, the initial heating stages of the system, such as Q_1 or Q_2 , present challenges due to the presence of copper heating processes (inertia) and the onset of start-up/dry-out phenomena. Specifically, an analysis based on MAD effectively distinguishes the differences

between these conditions, as illustrated in Figure 8. Values approaching zero correspond to dry-out conditions, whereas values exceeding the threshold denote start-up conditions.

Figure 8: Mean absolute deviation of thermal resistance in case of FR=70 %.

The measurement data collected were used to perform the interpolation presented in Figure 9. These three graphs summarize all the data obtained for the FRs analyzed, the inclination angles, and the power supplied. As mentioned above, the output parameter of these analyses is the thermal resistance R or equivalent effective thermal conductivity coefficient k_{eff} .

The analysis of the range of results clearly indicates that filling ratio of 70% is close to the optimal value, ranging from 0.5 K W^{-1} to a maximum of 2.5 K W^{-1} . This is verified by the fact that the $FR = 50\%$, and the thermal resistance ranged from 1 K W^{-1} to 7 K W^{-1} . For high FR tested, the range was from 1 K W^{-1} to 4.5 K W^{-1} .

The study was to analyze both quantitative and qualitative aspects of ther-

(a) FR = 50%.

(b) FR = 70%.

(c) FR = 80%.

Figure 9: 3D surface plot of the effects of power input and tilted angle on the heat transfer performance in an OHP charged with acetone and different filling ratio.

mal performance parameters using an equation to characterize the nature of working fluid flow within oscillating heat pipe. Equation (11) was used to discern operating modes that cover peaks in both pulsating and oscillating flows and in circulating flows.

From the results shown in Figure 9, the tilted angle significantly influences the heat transfer performance of the L-shape OHP, as detailed below:

- 0° : All degrees of filling ratio exhibited similar conditions. High thermal resistance (R) was observed, overheating and no second power change reached.
- 30° : At FR levels of 50 % and 70 %, thermal performance was similar. At 80 %, higher R was noted, alongside an extended power supply range (one additional level).
- 60° : The lowest R observed at $FR = 50\%$, but this had the narrowest power supply range. At 70 %, a slightly higher R was noted with a broader range, a trend mirrored by $FR = 80\%$.
- 90° : Identical R values were seen for 50 % and 70 %, with the latter showing a wider power range (one step more). For 80 %, R doubled compared to the others, with a similar maximum power range.
- 120° : $FR = 50\%$ performed worst. At 70 %, the lowest R was achieved, while higher FRs showed increased R but broader power range.
- 150° : Similar trends to 120° were observed.
- 180° : For 50 % and 70 %, R increased significantly, indicating ineffective heat exchange process. At $FR = 80\%$, relatively efficient thermal performance was observed, though R was 300 % higher than the optimal value in this study.

In summary, backward tilting did not achieve efficient thermal performance for the L-OHP, regardless of filling ratio, when in the horizontal position. Intermediate tilt angles performed similarly at 50 % and 70 %, providing better

results. Vertical positioning showed notably poor performance, especially at $FR = 80\%$, although 70% allowed for a wider power supply range. Forward tilting significantly degraded performance, reducing efficiency by approximately 50% across all angles. Intermediate tilts consistently exhibited around 12% higher thermal resistance at $FR = 80\%$, but they supported higher maximum power compared to 70% . In forward horizontal positions, only $FR = 80\%$ achieved relatively efficient heat exchange, while other filling ratios failed to reach the start-up conditions.

In order to perform validation of the presented results, no exact matching design was found in the literature that would allow for a direct comparison of the results obtained. Therefore, the analysis was based on data that closely resemble the system, particularly in terms of the working fluid used, such as acetone. In addition, designs with a vertical configuration were selected when no bending was applied. The results are presented in Table 7. Special attention was paid to publications discussing designs with an evaporator bent at a 90° angle or similar geometric features. However, the analysis did not consider differences arising from other design parameters, such as channel diameter, number of bends, or number of device layers, what is crucial in thermal analysis.

Table 7: Results comparison with literature data.

Source	WF	Vertical	$90^\circ_{vert.}$	$90^\circ_{hor.}$	Comments
[25]	Ethnaol	2.5	4	-	Polymer, different type and fluid
[11]	Acetone	0.09	-	-	-
[13]	Acetone	0.2	-	-	-
[14]	Acetone	0.5	-	-	-
[15]	Acetone	0.2	-	-	-
[16]	Acetone	0.1	-	-	-
[34]	Acetone	-	0.14	-	Reversed config. and rounded shape
[39]	HFE-7000	-	-	1.5	Different fluid and diameter
Present	Acetone	-	0.27	0.65	-

Due to the significant number of parameters that influence the thermal processes that occur in the L-shaped OHP and the problem of developing a physical

model, the authors would like to use in the future, in addition to quantitative investigations and optimization, the studies and algorithms presented in this article for analysis based on artificial intelligence AI, similar to those presented by Jiang et al. [46].

4. Summary and conclusions

This study explored the thermal performance of an L-shaped oscillating heat pipe across varying power supply levels, filling ratio values, and tilt angles, alongside a preliminary analysis of result reproducibility. The findings highlighted significant variability, with deviations in some cases exceeding the mean by up to 50%, underscoring the lack of consistent linear trends among test repetitions.

Distinct operational boundaries were identified based on tilt direction, emphasizing the role of Earth's gravitational acceleration. Backward tilts achieved optimal performance at an FR of 50%, while vertical positioning performed similarly to backward tilts for FRs of 50% and 70%, with the latter showing a slight advantage. Forward tilts were most effective at higher FRs (70% and 80%). Intermediate forward tilt angles favored an FR of 70%, whereas the horizontal position generally hindered performance except at an FR of 80%.

The results suggest that optimal thermal performance, particularly in forward-tilted configurations, requires ensuring adequate evaporator wetting through a proper filling ratio and aligning the evaporator's curvature with the gravitational acceleration vector. These findings provide valuable insights into designing and operating L-shaped OHPs for improved thermal efficiency.

Conflict of interest

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.

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